

Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) Complexes of some Bisheterocycles as Potential Fungicides. Part-II

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Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 2-[[5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-ylthio]methyl]-1H-benzimidazole (L₁); 3-[[5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)-4N-amino]-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylthio]methyl]-1H-benzimidazole (L₂) and 3-[[5-(2-furoyl)-4N-phenyl]-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylthio]methyl]-1H-benzimidazole (L₃) have been prepared and characterised. The complexes have been screened for their antifungal activities.

The biological activity of thiadiazoles and triazoles¹⁻³ and the synthetic utility of benzimidazole derivatives in building the organic heterocycles as chemotherapeutic agents are reported⁴. In view of these facts and in continuation to our recent interest in the study of various bisheterocycles⁵ and their metal chelates⁶, it was thought of interest to explore the ligational behaviour of some new benzimidazoles.

Results and Discussion

The empirical formulae of the metal complexes along with their physical and analytical data are given in Table 1. The molar conductances of the complexes (5–25 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicated their non-electrolytic nature in solution⁷.

In the ir spectra of the complexes, the free ligand band at 3 180–3 150 cm^{-1} (NH) remained constant showing non-participation of NH in coordination. However, the broad peak in the spectra of complexes at 3 500–3 200 cm^{-1} (coordinated H₂O) was found consistent with the number of H₂O estimated⁸. The insignificant lowering in the free ligand band at 1 620–1 600 cm^{-1} (C=N)⁹ in the spectrum of the complexes could be due to the presence of at least one uncoordinated C=N group in the ring. However, the increase in the $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ band of the free ring (1 040–1 200 cm^{-1}) by 10–20 cm^{-1} (Ref. 10) in the spectra of the metal complexes supported the coordination of at least one C=N group of the ring¹¹. The $\text{S} \rightleftharpoons \text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}$ group of the remaining heterocycle is considered as the other bond-

ing site of the ligands¹. The ν_{NH_2} band in the free ligand (L₂) observed at 3 300–3 200 cm^{-1} remained unaltered in the spectra of the complexes and is masked by $\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ band.

The magnetic moment (Table 1) and electronic spectral data were found consistent with the octahedral Ni^{II} (Ref. 12), tetrahedral Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes⁸. The geometry around Cu^{II} in the complexes could not be identified from these data alone. The lowering in the magnetic moment observed for the Ni^{II} complexes could be due to metal-metal interaction.

For the deeper understanding about the geometry of the Cu^{II} complexes, their esr spectra at liquid nitrogen temperature were recorded. A signal (Fig. 1) at half-field for [Cu(L₃)_{1/2}Cl₂·2H₂O] was observed in addition to g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values of 2.39 and 1.92 respectively, which indicated dimeric nature of the complex¹³ along with tetragonally distorted octahedral¹⁴ geo-

Fig. 1. Powder esr spectra of [Cu(L₃)_{1/2}Cl₂·2H₂O].

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. (°C)/ (Yield%)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						μ_{eff} B.M.
		C	H	N	M	S	Cl	
[Co(L ₁)Cl ₂]	300 (70.2)	36.48 36.89	2.45 2.17	10.54 10.12	10.32 10.65	11.82 11.57	25.12 25.68)	4.77
[Ni(L ₁) _{1/2} Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	170d (64.3)	27.23 27.04	2.44 2.12	7.53 7.42	16.28 15.56	8.86 9.48	28.75 28.23)	2.36
[Cu(L ₁)Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	306 (78.9)	34.43 34.37	2.42 2.69	9.64 9.43	10.24 10.69	10.26 10.78	24.54 23.92)	1.85
[Zn(L ₁)Cl ₂]	300 (60.2)	36.88 36.47	2.41 2.14	10.43 10.01	12.13 11.67	11.78 11.44	25.64 25.38)	Diamag.
[Co(L ₂)Cl ₂]	162d (65.3)	37.43 37.03	2.35 2.54	15.46 15.25	10.23 10.69	5.36 5.80	25.25 25.77)	4.99
[Ni(L ₂) _{1/2} Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	250 (71.4)	27.42 27.11	2.52 2.92	11.62 11.16	15.15 15.60	4.56 4.25	28.65 28.30)	2.59
[Cu(L ₂)Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O]	220d (59.2)	35.34 34.99	3.05 3.18	15.06 14.79	10.89 10.51	5.95 6.03	24.74 24.54)	1.79
[Zn(L ₂)Cl ₂]	225d (63.5)	36.30 36.60	2.20 2.51	15.40 15.07	12.12 11.71	6.26 5.74	25.08 25.47)	Diamag.
[Co(L ₃)Cl ₂]	225d (67.2)	47.63 47.72	2.72 2.98	13.64 13.91	11.45 11.71	6.64 6.36	14.38 14.11)	4.63
[Ni(L ₃)Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	125d (71.3)	44.74 44.54	3.32 3.53	12.86 12.99	11.36 10.87	6.46 5.94	13.62 13.17)	3.12
[Cu(L ₃) _{1/2} Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O]	210d (79.2)	33.46 33.61	3.46 3.22	9.46 9.80	17.64 17.78	4.73 4.48	20.25 19.88)	1.68
[Zn(L ₃)Cl ₂]	240 (80.4)	36.31 36.50	2.20 2.51	15.46 15.09	12.09 11.78	6.12 5.71	14.24 13.94)	Diamag.

Fig. 2. Powder esr spectrum of [Cu(L₂)Cl₂·H₂O].

metry around Cu^{II} with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state¹⁵. The solution (DMSO) spectrum of [Cu(L₁)Cl₂·2H₂O] at liquid nitrogen temperature produced g_{iso} as 2.08 which is consistent with distorted octahedral coordination around Cu^{II} in the complex¹⁶. The powder esr spec-

trum of [Cu(L₂)Cl₂·H₂O] at liquid nitrogen temperature (Fig. 2) afforded g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} as 1.96 and 2.04 respectively, with A_{\parallel} (⁶³Cu) and A_{\perp} (¹⁴N) as 50 and 15 gauss respectively. The trend $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel} > 2.0$ with a hyperfine structure due to the copper nucleus at the g_{\parallel} region although uncommon, has been documented in the literature for Cu^{II} having trigonal bipyramidal geometry with d_{z^2} ground state^{17,18}.

Thus on the basis of these spectral data and physical properties like the high thermal stability and insolubility of the complexes in common solvents, tentative dimeric/polymeric structure for the complexes could be proposed as shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

The fungicidal activity of each compound was determined¹⁹ against the fungi causing damage to local crops²⁰ at different concentrations as solution or

TABLE 2—ANTI-FUNGAL ACTIVITY (AVERAGE % INHIBITION) OF LIGANDS AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	<i>F. udum</i>		<i>P. aphanidermatum</i>		<i>R. solani</i>	
	Concn. (ppm)		Concn. (ppm)		Concn. (ppm)	
	4000	2000	4000	2000	4000	2000
(L ₁)	30	5	50	30	40	15
(L ₂)	15	0	100	50	44	15
(L ₃)	40	16	60	20	40	17
[Ni(L ₁) _{1/2} Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	90	35	60	15	60	30
[Co(L ₁)Cl ₂]	70	36	100	70	100	50
[Zn(L ₁)Cl ₂]	100	65	100	65	100	55
[Ni(L ₂) _{1/2} Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	30	15	70	25	40	15
[Co(L ₂)Cl ₂]	100	60	100	65	100	65
[Ni(L ₃)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	20	5	90	45	40	20
[Co(L ₃)Cl ₂]	15	7	100	36	75	35
[Zn(L ₃)Cl ₂]	35	8	100	48	55	25

L = L₁, L₂ and L₃
 X = Y = nil, M = Co^{II} and Zn^{II}
 L = L₂, X = H₂O, Y = nil, M = Cu^{II}
 L = L₁ and L₃, X = Y = H₂O, M = Cu^{II}

Fig. 3

L = L₁, L₂ and L₃
 M = Ni^{II}

Fig. 4

suspension in acetone. The metal complexes were found more fungitoxic than the free ligands (Table 2). This could be understood in terms of chelation theory⁹

stating that upon complexation the polarity of the metal ion gets reduced which increases the lipophilicity of the metal complexes facilitating them to cross the cell membrane easily. Furthermore, it is clear that four-coordinated complexes showed better fungitoxicity than six-coordinated Ni^{II} complexes. It is expected in view of the unsaturation of coordination number of the Co^{II} and Zn^{II}. These complexes might be competing with the functional groups of enzymes present in the fungi to complete their coordination number and hence hampering the enzymatic activity and showing better activity²¹.

Experimental

5-(2,4-Dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-2-ylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole : It was prepared using 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid hydrazide²³, m.p. 197°. Similarly, 5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-4*N*-amino-3-ylthio-1,2,4-triazole and 5-(furoyl)-4-phenyl-3-ylthio-1,2,4-triazole were prepared²³ using 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid hydrazide and furoyl-2-hydrazide respectively, as the starting materials.

*2-[15-(2,4-Dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-ylthio]methyl]-1*H*-benzimidazole (L₁)* : A mixture of 5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy-methyl)-2-ylthio-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2.93 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole²⁴ (1.70 g, 0.01 mol) in pyridine (15 ml) was gently heated on a water-bath for 4 h. The

reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water (250 ml). The resulting solid was washed with water followed by ethanol, and crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 47.42; H, 2.62; N, 12.45; S, 14.62; Cl, 18.74. $C_{17}H_{12}N_4OS_2Cl_2 \cdot 1/4HCl$ calcd. for : C, 47.20; H, 2.83; N, 12.95; S, 14.81; Cl, 18.55%).

3-[15-(2,4-Dichlorophenoxy)-4N-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylthio]methyl]-1H-benzimidazole (L_2) : A mixture of 5-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy)methyl)-4N-amino-3-ylthio-1,2,4-triazole (2.90 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole²⁴ (1.70 g, 0.01 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) was heated gently on a water-bath for 5 h, and after cooling at room temperature it was poured in ice-cold water (200 ml). Initially a gummy product was obtained, which solidified on being kept in a refrigerator for 48 h. The solid product was crystallised from ethanol, (3.20 g, 76%), m.p. 170° (Found : C, 48.67; H, 3.42; N, 19.86; S, 7.92; Cl, 16.46. $C_{17}H_{14}N_6OSCl_2$ calcd. for : C, 48.45; H, 3.32; N, 19.95; S, 7.60; Cl, 16.86%).

3-[5-(Furoyl)-4 phenyl-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylthio]methyl]-1H-benzimidazole (L_3) : 2-(4-Phenyl)furoylthiosemicarbazide was prepared by reacting furoic acid hydrazide with phenyl isothiocyanate²⁵. The thiosemicarbazide (13.0 g, 50 mol) in 8% aqueous NaOH was refluxed for 3 h. The insoluble part was filtered. The filtrate was neutralised with moderately concentrated HCl (5 N; 5 ml) to yield a colourless solid which was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. The ligand (L_3) was prepared by condensing 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole and 5-(2-furoyl)-4N-amino-3-ylthio-1,2,4-triazole in pyridine (10 ml), (2.40 g, 64%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 64.21; H, 4.12; N, 18.54; S, 8.83. $C_{20}H_{15}N_5OS$ calcd. for : C, 64.34; H, 4.02; N, 18.76; S, 8.57%).

Preparation of complexes. General procedure : An ethanolic solution (20 ml) of the ligand (20 mmol) was mixed with the ethanolic solution (10 ml) of the metal chlorides (2 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 5 h and the resulting solid was dried under reduced pressure. However, in the isolation of the Co^{II} complex with ligand (L_1), the pH (~8) of the reaction mixture was maintained by dropwise addition of 25% aque-

ous ammonia solution. The complexes of (L_2) with Ni^{II} and Co^{II} were isolated only after reducing the solvent from reaction mixture.

C, H and N were analysed in the Microanalytical Section of the Department. Metal, S and Cl were estimated by the standard procedure²⁶. Molar conductance was measured on a WTW conductivity bridge using $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solution of the complexes in DMSO. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on Cahn-Faraday electrobalance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constant²⁷. Electronic and IR spectra (nujol) were measured on Carry-14/Shimadzu and Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer respectively, and ESR spectra on a Varian E-4 X-band spectrometer at Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay.

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